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Analysis of Physico-chemical properties of Groundwater of Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh (India).

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the physico-chemical parameters of groundwater to determine its quality using geographical information system (GIS) and Bar diagram. We collected 50 Groundwater samples from different locations of the Mathura district, and analysed the Groundwater Quality of these samples on the basis of their pH, Turbidity, TDS, Total Hardness, Electrical conductivity, Calcium, Magnesium, Fluoride, NO₃, Chloride and Fe. During sample collection, (handling and preservation) standard procedures recommended by the American Public Health Association (APHA 2005) and Adoni et al., 1985 were followed to ensure data quality and consistency. Groundwater is a vital and purest form of natural resource, and the most economical source of drinking water for urban, rural and semi-urban areas in India. The analysis revealed that the quality of drinking water is not good in the study area, and it needs to be treated before drinking purpose. Both geogenic and anthropogenic factors are the major causes for high concentrations of various water quality parameters in the study area. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Hardness (TH), Fluoride, Magnesium, Electrical conductivity, Fe and chloride are found to be higher than permissible limit when compared with the guidelines of the WHO and BIS: 10500.

Key Words: Groundwater, Physico-chemical Parameters, GIS, TDS, TH, NITI, WHO and BIS

Introduction:

Ground water is a great gift of nature act as elixir of life. Thousands have lived without love, but no one could live without water (W.H. Auden). It is a major source of drinking water in both urban and rural areas of India. Water quality is a critical concern for all life, as without safe water all life and biological activities come to a halt. India is home to about 18 percent of the world's population and has only 4 percent of water resources, making it one of the most water-stressed countries in the world (World Bank). According to the Central Ground Water Board, per capita water availability in the country has declined by 70% from 1951 to 2011, i.e. in a period of 60 years. (India today) India has been ranked 141 out of 180 countries in the Yale University's Unsafe Drinking Water Index 2022(East Asia Forum). About 70 percent of India's water is contaminated. India is facing a severe water crisis, which causes the death of around 200,000 people every year. (National Institution transformation of India (NITI) Aayog- 2019)

(Salman et al., 2018) found that water quality in most parts of the mathura district, Uttar pradesh is unsuitable for drinking and irrigation purpose. The major cause of the high concentration of different water quality parameters is geogenic.

(Kanmani and Gandhimathi 2013) in their work found that the Ariyamangalam open dump site in Tiruchirappalli district of Tamil Nadu is a serious threat to local aquifers, and also (Hurra and Bhavsar 2021) found that the Bhanpur municipal solid waste dumping site in Bhopal is prone to groundwater contamination through leaching action. A considerable number of diseases can be prevented by improving access to safe water supply, periodic quality monitoring, providing adequate sanitation facilities and improved hygiene practices, especially in developing countries (Balan et al. 2012). (Qureshi and Armo 2022) reported in their study that the overall WQI of groundwater in Raya block, Mathura district, Uttar Pradesh falls in the poor categories as far as potability for human consumption is concerned, and recommended that groundwater in the study area is not suitable for direct human consumption. (Krishna Kumar Yadav et. al) in their study reported that groundwater samples collected from various places in Agra city, and all water samples do not comply with the standards of the World Health Organization and Indian Standards- 10500-91. There is a need to take precautionary measures before drinking groundwater in the Agra region, so that adverse health effects on humans can be prevented.

Study Area:

Mathura District is a medium-sized district in terms of population as well as area. It lies between latitudes 27° 14' and 27° 17' N and longitudes 77° 17' and 78° 12' E and bordered by the Gurgaon district of Haryana state in the North and Bharatpur district of Rajasthan state in the Northwest. In the northeastern and eastern sides, it is bounded by Aligarh and on the south by the district of Agra, was selected as the study area. It is about 141 kms away from the country's capital, New Delhi. Yamuna River flows from north to south through the Mathura district which divides the district into two physical units- western and eastern. The average monthly maximum temperature ranges between 36° C and 47° C in summer and 25° C and 32° C in winter, and the annual rainfall is 826 mm. During pre-monsoon periods the water is 2.65 to 14.34 m below ground level (bgl) and during post-monsoon, the levels are between 1.33 to 14.0 m bgl (CGWB, 2012). The persistent problem of high salinity and concentrations of other chemicals in groundwater is reported in previous studies (CGWB, 2012).

Figure: 1- Location of study area and sampling sites from where groundwater samples were collected for analytical analysis in Mathura district (Uttar Pradesh), India.

Methodology:

Total 50 Groundwater samples were collected from different government and domestic hand pumps during October-December (2023) from study area, representing the post-monsoon season. The location of the sampling sites is shown in Figure 1. ArcGIS 10 is used to map and bar diagram for the analysis of groundwater quality. Samples were collected by using High density polyethylene (HDPE) bottles. The samples were filled completely and sealed immediately in order to avoid contact with air. The labeled samples were analyzed for various physicochemical parameters in the laboratory. During sample collection, (handling and preservation) standard procedures recommended by the American Public Health Association (APHA 2005) and Adoni *et al.*, 1985 were followed to ensure data quality and consistency. The groundwater characterization has been carried out for the parameters like pH, Turbidity, total hardness (TH), calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), chloride (Cl^-), Electrical Conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), nitrate (NO_3^-), Iron (Fe) and fluoride (F). The obtained results were compared World Health Organization (WHO) and Bureau of Indian Standards 10500 (BIS). TDS and electrical conductivity measured by Fisher AB-200 digital meter, and pH by Fisher AB-150. Calcium (Ca^{2+}), Magnesium, Total hardness (TH), and chloride (Cl^-) were analysed by volumetric titration method. Nitrate (NO_3^-) was analysed by UV spectrophotometer.

To determine the fluoride in groundwater samples Colorimetric method (SPANDS) was used. While Iron was analyzed by the phenanthroline method. At 25°C, the concentration of EC is expressed in microsiemens/cm whereas TDS, Calcium, Total Hardness, nitrate, Magnesium, Chloride, Iron (Fe) and Fluoride are expressed in mg /l.

Result and discussions:

The physico-chemical concentrations of collected groundwater samples for the various parameters like maximum, minimum and mean are shown in Table No.1.

pH indicates whether a solution is alkaline, neutral or acidic. It is a measure of the concentration of hydrogen ions in water. As per (BIS, 2012) the pH required has to be in the range of 6.5–8.5 for the drinking purpose. In present study pH

concentration is ranges from 6.6 to 8.2 which shows that it is within the permissible limit as prescribed by BIS (2012). The lowest value was observed in M20 and highest value was recorded in M31(Fig.2).

Fig.2: Variation in pH at different sampling stations in study area.

Turbidity: High turbidity causes the water to appear cloudy or muddy due to the presence of particulate matter such as clay or sludge, finely divided organic matter, etc. Turbidity is an optical property of water, not a chemical or biological measurement.

High turbidity levels and low turbidity levels do not necessarily indicate poor water quality or good water quality, respectively. Caution should be exercised when using turbidity as a water quality parameter. Therefore, the values should be evaluated in conjunction with other parameters. The turbidity in the groundwater samples was determined using the Turbidity meter following Nephelometric method (EPA,2021). In present study, turbidity in groundwater samples ranges from 0.9 to 10.1 was observed. The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M9 (Fig.3).

Fig.3: Variation in turbidity at different sampling stations in study area.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS): TDS comprise inorganic salts (principally calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), sodium potassium, chlorides (Cl) bicarbonates, and sulfates) and small amounts of organic matter that are dissolved in water (WHO,2006). TDS in drinking-water originate from natural sources, urban runoff, sewage, and industrial wastewater. The concentration of TDS in water varies considerably in different geological regions due to differences in the solubility of minerals (WHO, 2006). TDS in groundwater samples ranges from 610 Milligrams per litre(mg/l) to 8160 mg/l with a mean of 2624 mg/l. However, high amount of Total dissolve solids in study area indicating severe contamination and health threat. High TDS increases the density of water, reduces the solubility of gases such as oxygen and ultimately makes the water unfit for drinking (WHO, 1984). High TDS level greater than 500 mg/l result in excessive scaling in water pipes, boilers, water heater and household appliances (Tihansky, 1974). Similarly, Hurra and Bhavsar, 2021 reported the TDS results of groundwater in Bhanpur, Bhopal district. All 50 collected samples in this study region are higher than the permissible limit value. The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M10 (Fig. 4).

Fig.4: Variation in TDS at different sampling stations in study area.

Electrical conductivity (EC): It is a measure of water's ability to transmit electric current, it is one of the important physico-chemical parameters that helps in determining water quality. As per the (WHO-2016) the highest desirable limit of EC in drinking water is 750 microsiemens per centimeter ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). The observed value of Electrical Conductivity in water samples is between 940 and 12855 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with a mean value of 3917 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in of 50 sample. 48 samples have value higher than 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in the study region. The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M10 (Fig.5).

Fig.5: Variation in Electrical Conductivity at different sampling stations in study area.

Total Hardness (TH): Total hardness refers to the sum of the calcium and magnesium concentration in water, and both expressed as CaCO_3 in mg/l . Total hardness is calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Total hardness (mg/l)} = \frac{\text{volume of titrant}(t) \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

Total hardness is one of the most important parameters in water quality assessment. Total Hardness in the study area ranged from 205 to 1920, with a mean value of 684 milligrams per litres (Mg/l). The WHO standard for TH is 500 mg/l (All 50 samples of study region fall outside this range). Hardness represents a combined measure of polyvalent cations with calcium and magnesium being the primary components of hardness (Larry, 1996). The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M40 (Fig.6).

Fig.6: Variation in Total hardness at different sampling stations in study area.

Calcium and Magnesium: Water containing high amounts of magnesium or calcium is considered hard and is undesirable for domestic purposes. The values of calcium range from 22 mg/l to 193 mg/l with a mean value of 61.3 mg/l (Table 1). The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M40 (Fig.7).

The concentration of magnesium is very high in groundwater samples. The observed data shows that the values lie in the non-permissible range in most parts of the mathura district. It ranges from 44.4 mg/l to 419 mg/l with a mean value of 150.71mg/l. The lowest value was observed in M4 and the highest value was recorded in M40 in pre monsoon season (Fig.8). The calcium hardness was calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Calcium hardness mg/l as CaCO}_3 = \frac{\text{Volume of titrant(t) used} \times 1000 \times 1.05}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

And Magnesium concentration was calculated by subtracting calcium hardness from total hardness of ground water.

$$\text{Mg (mg/l)} = [\text{Total hardness (as CaCO}_3\text{mg/l)} - \text{Calcium hardness (as CaCO}_3\text{ mg/l)}] \times 0.244$$

Fig.7: Variation in calcium at different sampling stations in study area.

Fig.8: Variation in magnesium at different sampling stations in study area.

Chloride (Cl): Chloride in excess imparts a salty taste to water, and people who are allergic to high chloride are subjected to laxative effects (Anitha et al.2011; Sadat-Noori et al. 2014). In the study area chloride concentration ranges from 54 mg/l to 2481 mg/l. Chlorides are found in natural water due to leaching of chloride containing rocks and soils discharges of effluents from chemical industries such as sewage disposal, ice-cream plant effluent, irrigation drainage (Saleem et al, 2018). 62 percent samples are found to be value higher than desirable limit of Chloride prescribed by BIS, 2012) for drinking water (Table-2). The results were expressed in mg/l. The lowest value was observed in M26 and the highest value was recorded in M28 (Fig.9).

The chloride content was calculated by using formula:

$$\text{Chloride in mg l}^{-1} = \frac{\text{Volume of titrant(t)used} \times N \times 35.46 \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

Where,

N= normality of AgNo₃(0.0141 N)

Fig.9: Variation in chloride at different sampling stations in study area.

Fluoride (F): High concentrations of fluoride cause dental and skeletal fluorosis while fluoride in low concentrations has beneficial effects on teeth by preventing and reducing the risk of tooth decay (Arumugam 2010), BIS and WHO standards for fluoride is 1.5 mg/l, values were found ranging between 0.2 mg/l to 3.9 mg/l in study area. 58 percent samples are found to be value higher than permissible limit of Fluoride prescribed by BIS, 2012) and WHO (2017for drinking water (Table-2). The lowest value was observed in M26 and the highest value was recorded in M10 in (Fig.10).

Fig10.: Variation in fluoride at different sampling stations in study area.

Nitrate: Increased nitrate contamination poses a serious threat to public drinking water supplies and human health. Nitrate concentrations in the study area ranged from 1 mg/l to 56 mg/l. The lowest value was observed in M30 and the highest value was recorded in M5 in post monsoon season (Fig.11). Except a few sampling points, the study area is falling under the desirable limit as shown in Table 1. Nitrate concentrations above 45 mg/l (BIS, 2009) cause methemoglobinemia (blue baby syndrome), gastric cancer, thyroid disease and diabetes (Krishna Kumar et al., 2011)

Fig.11: Variation in Nitrate at sampling stations in study area.

Iron: Iron occurs naturally in aquifers, but the disintegration of iron borehole and hand pump components can lead to increased levels in groundwater. Iron-rich groundwater is often coloured orange, discolouring laundry, and has an unpleasant taste, which is evident in drinking and food preparation. Iron values were found ranging between 0.02 mg/l to 4.1 mg/l. The lowest value was observed in M27 and the highest value was recorded in M10 (Fig.12). BIS (2012) permissible limit for Iron for drinking water <0.3mg/l as well as WHO (2017) has fixed it to be <0.3 mg/l.

Fig.12: Variation in iron at sampling stations in study area.

Table 1: Statistical groundwater quality parameter compared with BIS (2012) and WHO (2017).

S. NO.	Parameter	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	BIS (2012)		WHO (2017)
						Desirable limit	Permissible Limit	
1.	TDS	610	8160	2624	1987.22	500	2000	500
2.	EC	940	12855	3084	3009.52	-	-	750
3.	TH	205	1920	684	370.16	200	600	500
4.	F ⁻	0.22	3.9	1.75	0.76	1	1.5	1.5
5.	Cl ⁻	54	2481	892.4	677.63	250	1000	250
6.	Ca ²⁺	22	193	61.3	31.75	75	200	75
7.	Mg ⁺²	44.4	419.6	150.7	81.96	30	100	30
8.	NO ₃ ⁻¹	1	56	26.67	14.1	45	-	50
9.	Fe	0.02	4.1	1.0214	1	0.3	-	0.3

Table 2: - Sample number assigned to sampling area selected for groundwater analysis from Mathura district.

S. No.	Sampling No.	Sample Site Name
1	M1	Hayatpur Village
2	M2	SMT Shanti Devi Secondary School, Jugsana
3	M3	Baldeo Chauraha
4	M4	Near Mandir Dauji, Baldeo
5	M5	Mahavan-Bangar, Near Madan Kheer Mohan Waale
6	M6	Shergarh Chauraha

7	M7	Chhata, Goverdhan Road
8	M8	Dautana
9	M9	Akbarpur
10	M10	Kosikalan, Mathura-Delhi Road Highway
11	M11	Jait village
12	M12	Near Chaumuhan Chauraha
13	M13	Akbarpur Village
14	M14	Ahuri
15	M15	Ajhaj Khurd
16	M16	Near Toll plaza -Agra- Delhi Road
17	M17	Farah-Main Bazar
18	M18	Luhara Village
19	M19	Daulatpur Village
20	M20	Barari Village
21	M21	Malhu at banJar Penth
22	M22	Sakitara, Near Primary Pathshala
23	M23	Palson village
24	M24	Sonkh Dehat,
25	M25	Chandauli Village
26	M26	Near Nahar(canal), Raya-Mant Road
27	M27	Mant Tehsil
28	M28	Near Primary School, Chhahri Village
29	M29	Ram Nagala Village
30	M30	Taitigaon, at Tiraha
31	M31	Aganpura Village
32	M32	Near GLA University
33	M33	Vrindavan Khadar
34	M34	Jhikhangaon Village
35	M35	Lakshiminagar Tiraha
36	M36	Lodhauri Village
37	M37	Near Petrol Pump, Barsana
38	M38	Kadauna, Near Primary School
39	M39	Kosikalan, Gopal Nagar
40	M40	Hasanpur Nagla
41	M41	Baghai Bangar Village
42	M42	Holi Chowk, Shergarh-Naujheel Road
43	M43	Makhdoompur village
44	M44	Birju Garhi village
45	M45	Hasanpur village
46	M46	Infront of Momin Mosque, Sultan Ganj
47	M47	Katra Bazar (Raya), Near Agrasen Chauk
48	M48	Karab Village, Near Kachaudi stall, Baldeo-Raya Road
49	M49	Koyal village, Hathras-Aligarh-Raya Road
50	M50	Gaju Village

Conclusion:

The results of the present study showed that most of the parameters such as total dissolved solids, fluoride, iron, Electrical Conductivity, total hardness (TH), Mg²⁺ and Chloride were found to be higher than the permissible limits as compared to the guidelines of World Health Organization and BIS. Both natural and anthropogenic factors are the major causes for high concentrations of various water quality parameters. The groundwater quality in Mathura district is in the poor category for human consumption. It is suggested that appropriate measures and treatment methods should be implemented before consumption of water for drinking purpose.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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